

PEDAGOGICAL METHODS WHICH ARE IMPORTANT IN TEACHING FOREIGN LITERATURE.

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Abstract: The role of communication, including intercultural communication and literature, is increasing in modern human life. But in our relations with representatives of other nations, we inevitably proceed from the existing ideas (heterostereotypes) about them, one of the sources of which is fiction. Therefore, in order to understand (not always consciously) how inter-ethnic communication is built, it is important to explain the images of representatives of certain nationalities that are depicted in the field of artistic creation.

Key words: national spirit, literature, people, England and America, writers and poets.

Literature is a criterion that expresses the national spirit of the most developed peoples in the world in terms of the fact that it has been able to preserve the national spirit and has been able to rise to a large scale in the variety of artistic images and styles. English literature has its own characteristics, which arise from the uniqueness of the country's culture, social and political development. It corresponds to the 19th century, defined the problems of literature and its forms. English writers, first of all, the novel develops at this stage, looked for their heroes not among bankers and aristocrats, but among those who sought to gain a career, as in France - their heroes were also small owners, like J. Eliot ("The Mill on the Floss"), even workers such as E. Gaskell ("Mary Barton") or Charles Dickens ("Hard Times"). Indeed, under the mask of calmness, a weak person may be hiding, filled with the desire to appear strong and invulnerable. External objectivity is characteristic of gentlemen in literature (Pickwick, Forestier, Worcester, etc.), as well as characters who keep secrets. The theory of the English national character, considered in the literary and journalistic works of English and American writers and poets, is a harmonious and integral part of the philosophical and worldview system. and turns into comments about the fate of the state and society. The destiny of the European person, the problems of mutual understanding between the representatives of different civilizations, the representatives of the East and the West, and ultimately, the meaning of life can be considered through the study of literature. Great representatives of English culture and literature raised the ideas of humanism and defended the interests of working people in their works. They used the achievements of ancient Greek and Roman culture and literature to uphold their life-giving traditions.

To some extent, England can be considered the ancestral homeland of romanticism. The first bourgeois development there gave birth to the first anti-bourgeois aspirations typical of the Romantics. Over the past century, English literature has depicted many important features of the romantic worldview: ironic self-regard, anti-rationalism, ideas about "incomprehensible things", the pursuit of "antiquity". The impetus for the emergence of English romanticism was both external and internal events - at this time, the industrial revolution took place in England. Its consequences are not only the substitution of the spinning wheel for the weaving machine, muscle power for the steam engine, but also profound social changes: the disappearance of the peasantry, the emergence of the industrial proletariat, the establishment of the bourgeoisie as "masters" was installed. from life". English humanism, which began to develop from the end of the 14th century, experienced its highest stage in the 16th century and the beginning of the 17th century. One of the first major representatives of English humanism is Geoffrey Chaucer 1340-1400. He was born in a merchant family. He enjoys the creativity of the representatives of the Italian and French Renaissance, he is one of the people close to King Edward 3, and he participates in military campaigns and wars with him. The first great success of Chaucer's work can be seen in his poem "The Book of the Duchess" 1369. This lyrical poem does not adhere to the old beliefs that prevailed in the poetry of the Middle Ages, and humanistic feelings characteristic of the Renaissance began to shine in this work. In it, the poet sings about the pains of the knight who was separated from his queen due to the untimely death of his queen. In the process of describing, the poet often refers to the lives of the heroes of the high world, which to some extent expresses the interest of the Renaissance period in the world of the ancient world.

Chaucer's works such as "House of Fame (1379-1384), "Council of Birds" (1377-1382), "Troil and Chryseida" (1372-1384) also have the spirit of that period. M. Gorky assessed Chaucer as the artist who "founded realism". Chaucer's Canterbury Tales is composed of 1,367 stanzas and contains stories similar to the Decameron. A group of 29 people from all walks of life gather at Harry Bailey's Hotel to visit the grave of St. Thomas Baker in Canterbury. they come out. Since the destination is far, they take turns to tell four stories on the way back and forth. Because the knights, merchants, monks, peasants, students, peasants and other people of different classes are included in the stories, the stories reflect the lives of people of different classes. It was a period when deep self-awareness and the struggle for national unity among the British people intensified, and a new spiritual upliftment began to take place in the field of culture and literature.

V. Shakespeare (1564-1616), who came out of the people, began to gain great fame with his great talent from his first works. He was born in a small town called Sretford, his father was a craftsman who made leather hats. At the age of 18, he married a farmer's daughter named Anna Hentway and had a daughter named Suzanne and sons named Jude and Hamlet. Shakespeare came to London in 1587 and started working in the theater. They start work as prompters and quickly become writers known to the whole world. During his entire career, Shakespeare wrote 154 sonnets, 37 poems and two plays, and Shakespeare scholars divide his work into 3 periods. In the 1st period of Shakespeare's work, which includes the years 1590-1601, "The Comedy of Delusions", "The Casting of the Deer Maiden", "The Two Young Men of Veronica", "Love's Vain Increase", "A Midsummer Night's Dream", "The Clowns of Windsor", Comedies such as "A lot of fuss", "Do you like this?", "Twelfth night" and "Henry 4", "Richard 3", "King John", "Richard 2", "Henry 4", " He wrote such famous tragedies as Henry V, Romeo and Juliet, and Julius Caesar. In the second period covering the years 1601-1608, tragic works expressing great humanist ideas such as "Hamlet", "Othello", "Cyrol Lear", "Macbeth", "Antony and Cleopatra", "Coriolanus", "Timon of Athens" creates. In the third period of Shakespeare's work (1608-1612), he mainly wrote tragicomedies such as "Symbeline", "Winter's Tale", "The Tempest", and turned to more fairy-tale plots in them, and looked confidently at the future of mankind. Creativity T. Capote. The story "Breakfast at Tiffany's": problems, characteristics of the main character. The novel In Cold Blood: A Parable of Modern America. Features of the "non-fiction novel" genre.

The Confessional Lyric of the 1960s: R. Lowell, S. Plath. The poet's life as a material for understanding modernity. R. Lowell: meditative lyricism, confessionalism and autobiography combined with historical and philosophical reflections. R. Lowell on the poet as a prophet and teacher of the people. Literary movement "Beatniks": existentialist and naturalistic tendencies in their work (J. Kerouac and others). The development of realism in the 1960s and 1970s: the novels of Cheever, Styron, etc. Warren's novel All the King's Men. "Lovely" novel by T. Morrison.

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